

Special issue on:

Marketing and Consumer Behavior in the Digital Environment

IMPORTANT DATES:

Submission of Full Paper: until July 31, 2024.

Initial decision sent to authors: until November 31, 2024

Deadline for revised papers: February 28, 2025

Notification of acceptance: until March 30, 2025

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MAIN TOPIC:

Nowadays, due to the emergence of digital platforms for doing business (e.g. social media platform (Colicev et al., 2018), marketing, sales, blogs for culture experience) and its efficiency in terms of ROI, content generating, influencer life (Cai & Choi, 2023), consumers, government and firms have been moving their efforts towards the digital marketing landscape.

Even offline operations are aligned to online through omnichannel strategies (Gasparin & Slongo, 2023) in order to provide a better customer experience (Floriano & Silva, 2023) and have better results (e.g. revenue and profit). The economy digitalization and the use of digital marketing strategies, concepts, channels and tools are paramount (Vieira et al., 2023). Some scholars called this as Digital Era (Kumar, et al., 2022; Vaishnav & Ray, 2023). From digital ads (Becheri et al., 2023; Isabella et al., 2023b) and social media marketing, to search engine marketing optimization and analytics, what we are seeing is the emergence of symbolic means, consumer culture, and organizational strategies focuses on digital environment.

Doing so, this scenario brings at least many challenges for companies, governments, social movements, researchers and practitioners. The first one is regarding the firm's viewpoint as responsible for either investing on digital marketing or adopting strategies, brands, business models (Heldt et al., 2021), concepts and tools. The second one takes the consumer's viewpoint, who is affected (or affect) by the use of digital marketing across the customer journey (Santini et al., 2020) or does activism (Zanette, 2023). The third one takes the market' dynamic viewpoint (Castilhos et al., 2017), which deals with micro and macro marketing (Sauerbronn et al., 2022), alternative markets, market institutions, society, and anthropologic view of markets. The fourth one takes the transformative consumer and service side (Gouveia & Ayrosa, 2020), which discuss digital environmental for discussing problems such as privacy (Richarde et al., 2023), racism (Brouard et al., 2023), hunger, obesity, food policy, refugees, and citizenship.

As the usage of internet platforms and technology expands, digital marketing has become an increasingly significant component of modern corporate transactions (Appel et al., 2020). The Associate Editors (AEs) expect that this call for papers contribute to the discussion on how industry, consumers, institutions, and marketing academia can face those challenges inherent to Internet (Toledo et al., 2004), e-commerce environmental (Santos et al., 2015), collaborative networks (Scaraboto, 2017) and consumer behavior.

AIMS AND SCOPE OF THE SPECIAL ISSUE

The call-for-papers is open to consider papers with dissimilar marketing or consumption (CCT) studies that consider “digital” as (a) the context of investigation, (b) data source, (c) analytical perspective, (d) phenomenon, and/or (e) the locus for knowledge application.

INVESTIGATION POSITIONING

The Associate Editors are looking to publish cutting-edge research papers with a wide range of methodologies, theories, concepts, models and applications on any aspect of digital marketing. The call-for-papers is also open to consider papers with different approaches, e.g. (a) theoretical papers (e.g. frameworks, taxonomies, and future research), (b) historical papers (e.g. timeline and era investigations), (c) quantitative papers (e.g. experiment, panel data, and surveys) and (d) interpretative perspectives (ethnography, (net)ethnography, in deep interview, projective technique, case studies, etc).

LIST OF THEMES FOR PUBLICATION

Therefore, consider the following list of themes for publication in this special issue, but is not limited to:

- a) Multichannel, marketing, channels and online retail strategy;
- b) Online advertising, owned media, paid media, search engine marketing, web analytics and performance;
- c) Social media marketing, social commerce, and social network analysis;
- d) The ontological perspective that shapes market studies, focusing in elements, such as reactivity, materiality, and media technologies in digital contexts of consumption;
- e) Consumers' roles in shaping contemporary market forms and practices, ranging from structuralism of the market, practice and culture to flat ontologies such as Actor-Network Theory;
- f) Culture and consumption of social media marketing (CCT);
- g) Digital marketing activities supported by AI tools technologies (Isabella et al., 2023a);
- h) Artificial intelligence and customer journey on digital market environment;
- i) Marketing segmentation and positioning based on machine learning (Brei et al., 2023);
- j) Customer experience and consumer culture, which explore consumption, discourses, meanings, socio-materiality, influences, practices in digital settings.

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